

A new method for synthesizing pentazole

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1 synthetic route

The amide is first diazotized at low temperatures to form an acyl diazonium salt, which undergoes click chemistry with the azide. Then wake up is carried out, the pentazole is easy to leave and removes the acyl group easily.

Acyl diazonium salts are unstable and must be prepared and reacted in situ by cooling in a dry ice-ethanol bath.

$Cu(I)$ ions can complex with diazonium salts, which is similar to the reaction of $Cu(I)$ ions with alkynes, and the complexes can react with azides to produce pentazoles.

Pentazole is more acidic and has good dissociative properties, and acyl pentazoles can be hydrolyzed to pentazole ions.

The catalyst is removed after the reaction to prevent decomposition of the products.

2 synthesis experiment

I used acetamide. The solution turned green in reaction. Addition of sodium hydroxide produces sodium pentazole.

Infrared spectra of the product (ethanol solution of crude sodium pentazole)

There are multiple absorption peaks in the region of wavenumbers $1700\text{--}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the infrared spectrogram, which is the characteristic absorption region of aromatic compounds and is consistent with the product.

3 References

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